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Executive Summary

The DECICE project aims to develop an AI-based, open and portable cloud management framework for automatic and adaptive optimization and deployment of applications in a federated infrastructure, including computing from the very large (e.g., HPC systems) to the very small (e.g., IoT sensors connected on the edge).

This document provides information on the **main digital resources and channels**, which were implemented as part of the DECICE project. First, the **visual design concept** presents the colour scheme, logo and identity kit including the print materials and screen designs. Second, the document outlines the project **website**, the central tool for keeping the public informed about the DECICE project. The website is divided in seven pages to ensure an easy navigation. Furthermore, the **social media channels (Twitter and LinkedIn)** and the **newsletter** are presented, which were set up as the project's digital distribution and dissemination tools. Finally, the document provides a **summary** of the main facts in the conclusion. Both the project website and the social media channels represent a vital step for the project's communication and dissemination activities aimed at presenting up-to-date insights to relevant stakeholders. All of the project consortium **partners** will contribute to the growth of the set-up communication channels by either sharing, liking, subscribing, following, engaging or posting regularly.

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Acronyms & Abbreviations

Term	Description
AI	Artificial Intelligence
CMS	Content Management System
CTA	Call-to-Action
D	Deliverable
DEC	Dissemination, Exploitation, and Communication
DoA	Description of the action
e.g.	example giving
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
HTTPS	Hypertext Transfer Protocol Secure
ID	Identification
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
QR	Quick Response
PC	Personal Computer
PHP	Personal Home Page Tool /Hypertext Preprocessor
SEO	Search Engine Optimisation
T	Task
WP	Work Package

1 Introduction

This document provides an **overview of the main digital resources and channels**, which were implemented as part of the DECICE project. This deliverable reports the published project website, as well as the set up social media channels and newsletter. First, the **visual design concept** presents the colour scheme, logo and identity kit including the print materials and screen designs.

Second, the document outlines the project **website**, the central tool for keeping the public informed about the DECICE project. The website is divided in seven pages to ensure an easy navigation and highlights the social media channels prominently. The *HOME* page represents the first impression and provides a brief overview on the project. Followed by the *NEWS* page which presents the latest project updates regularly. The content is provided evenly by all Consortium partners. Furthermore, an *EVENT* page was established to create an overview of topic related events for internal and external usage. Events organised by DECICE as well as events where DECICE will attend and present the project are emphasised. Besides presenting the latest developments and events, the website provides relevant information about the project background, objectives, facts, concept, impacts and structure on the *ABOUT* page. The website also presents all 13 consortium partners on the *CONSORTIUM* page with a short description and links to their websites and social media channels. Additionally, the *MEDIA* page provides an overview of all print materials, DECICE Logos, presentations etc. ready to download. Finally, the *CONTACT* page offers the opportunity to contact the DECICE team. The website will be continuously updated throughout the project showing the progress of public deliverables and dissemination materials. Whenever appropriate or necessary, new sections or subsections will be created.

After the website presentation, the **social media channels Twitter and LinkedIn** are presented in this deliverable. Social media is a further main approach to promote the DECICE project and essential for creating a strong network of innovators, researchers and other key stakeholders. The links to those social media platforms are embedded on the landing page and *CONTACT* page as well as prominently placed along the *User Journey* on the website. In the future, further social media channels (e.g., YouTube) will be set up whenever the consortium considers it necessary.

The **newsletter** is an additional tool to disseminate information, results and events. The newsletter subscription is placed directly on the *HOME* page and on the *NEWS* page of the DECICE website as well as posted and pinned at the Social Media accounts.

Finally, the document provides a **summary** of the main facts in the conclusion. Both the project website and the social media channels represent a vital step for the project's communication and dissemination activities aimed at presenting up-to-date insights to relevant stakeholders. All project consortium partners contribute to the growth of communication channels by either sharing, liking, subscribing, following, engaging or posting regularly. Outside of that, the partners will inform interested parties on events about possibilities to stay updated about the DECICE project like the website, social media, newsletter etc.

1.1 Relation to Other Tasks and Deliverables

This deliverable is related to the following other DECICE tasks and deliverables:

Receives inputs from:

Table 1: D6.3 Input from Other Tasks and Deliverables

Deliverable	Due Date	Input for D6.3
D6.1	31.05.2023 (M6)	Dissemination and Communication Plan
T6.1	M01-M36	Dissemination and Communication
T6.3	M18- M36	Establish an Online and Media Presence
T6.4	M01-M36	Public Outreach and Engagement with Existing Projects and Networks

Provides outputs to:

Table 2: D6.3 Output for Other Tasks and Deliverables

Deliverable	Due Date	Output from D6.3
D6.3	31.10.2024 (M24)	Online and Media Presence Update
T6.3	M18- M36	Establish an Online and Media Presence
D6.1	31.05.2023 (M6)	Dissemination and Communication Plan
D6.1	31.10.2024 (M24)	Dissemination and Communication Plan Update
T6.1	M1-M36	Dissemination and Communication

1.2 Structure of the Deliverable

Section 2 provides an overview of the project’s visual design concept including the colour scheme, logo and identity kit with print materials and screen design. In **section 3**, the website structure and every subpage are visualised and explained. **Section 4** outlines the social media channels and activities, and **section 5** describes the project newsletter. **Section 6** concludes the deliverable with a summary of the most important points.

2 Visual Design Concept

The visual design concept focuses on the aesthetically pleasing presentation of DECICE as a brand by strategically selecting and placing of colours, fonts, typography and layout. Furthermore, it is intended to guarantee accessibility, usability and legibility. First, the selection of the colour scheme and design are described. Subsequently, the logo design process and the final logo design are presented. Finally, the typography and fonts as well as the typographic scale matching the DECICE project identity are highlighted.

2.1 Colour Scheme

One of the most important determinants influencing perception in branding and advertising is colour. When selecting a colour, it is important to understand that colours have different meanings and symbolism across countries and cultures. With regards to the positioning of DECICE, we decided to use two colours which are close on the colour wheel, namely blue and violet. The colour blue is very commonly used in combination with any shade of purple. Creativity as meaning of violet and the thoughtful calm of the shades of blue are a perfect mix and gives the DECICE colour scheme (cf Fig. 1) its balance. [1] In addition, blue is associated with security, trustworthiness and therefore often used in corporate or cybersecurity matters. [2] More information about the meaning of the DECICE colour scheme can be found in D6.1. Dissemination & Communication Plan.

Figure 1: DECICE Colour Scheme and Meaning

2.2 Logo

Out of 13 logo drafts, three have been pre-selected internally and subsequently rated by the consortium via **logo poll** (cf Fig. 2).

Finally, the DECICE colour scheme was integrated in the **chosen DECICE logo** and negative versions of the logo in black and white were created. Of course, the final DECICE logo was also adapted to different use-case specific versions and application scenarios. Additionally, an icon/favicon of the logo (cf Fig. 3) was created. More insight about the process of the logo creation will be given in D6.1 Dissemination and Communication Plan.

Starting with the colour scheme and logo, the project identity was complemented by appealing fonts. More details can be found under 2.3 Identity Kit.

2.2.1 Logo Poll

Figure 2: DECICE Logo Poll

2.2.2 DECICE Final Logo, Icon and Favicon

Figure 3: DECICE Final Logo, Icon and Favicon

2.3 Identity Kit

In the first month of the project SYNYO focused on creating all relevant reference documents (e.g., deliverable and presentation templates) and developing the project identity including the logo, colour scheme, fonts and all basic designs for communication and dissemination such as print materials and

screen designs. Examples for print materials are leaflets, posters, folders, roll-ups, business cards, stickers etc. Designs for online usage were needed for the social media accounts like banners and post templates, website design and a power point presentation template for the consortium.

This project kit includes all the required elements for project communication and dissemination available in one place, and allows to easily present the project, its aims, activities and results in different contexts.

2.3.1 Identity Overview

The identity overview (cf Fig. 4) is the essential part in the identity kit and provides the consortium with all necessary information at once. Reaching from the logo and its proper use, colours and fonts.

Figure 4: DECICE Identity Overview

2.3.2 Print Materials

Experienced graphic designers at SYNNO created all print materials ensuring the project identity. In addition to the visual design, the consortium focused on high quality material with a good value for money. Those diverse print materials, such as leaflets, folders, business cards and stickers can be distributed during events, for example. Furthermore, roll-ups and posters attract interested parties and provide a good insight on the DECICE project.

Figure 5: DECICE Leaflet Front/Back

Figure 6: DECICE Folder Front/Back

Roll Up

Figure 7: DECICE Roll-Up

Business Cards

Figure 8: DECICE Business Cards

Stickers

Figure 9: DECICE Sticker – Logo

Figure 10: DECICE Sticker – Icon

2.3.3 Screen Design

Additional to the print materials, SYNYO created screen designs using the project identity design.

Social Media Banners

Figure 11: DECICE Social Media Banner

Figure 12: DECICE Social Media Profile Image

Social Media Post Templates

Figure 13: DECICE Social Media Post Templates

PowerPoint Template

Figure 14: DECICE Presentation Template

3 Project Website

The DECICE project website is available via <https://www.decice.eu/>. It is one of the main communication tools of the project and will promote and disseminate the project and its results.

The DECICE website is built using WordPress [3], a free and open-source Content Management System (CMS) platform based on PHP, MySQL, and JavaScript, which allows the quick deployment of modern, easily accessible and web browser compatible websites. As such, the website template utilises a dynamic web layout, which enables automatic and responsive size adjustments according to the screen display of the device in use; either it is a PC, a tablet or a smartphone. Moreover, the website uses the appropriate logo for the favicon, which further strengthens the DECICE project visual identity.

The website is using SEO (Search Engine Optimization) for better indexing and reaching on search engines such as Google, Bing and more.

3.1 Website Structure

The DECICE project website is structured into seven main areas. Figure 15 shows the high-level sitemap of the website. In the following sections, each page and (sub)page on the website is briefly described.

On every side the website provides the header including the menu bar to navigate between *HOME*, *NEWS*, *EVENTS*, *ABOUT*, *CONSORTIUM*, *MEDIA* and *CONTACT* and the link to the social media accounts. All pages include the Footer as well at the bottom, where the DECICE logo, the EU Funding Text, Contact of the Coordinator, Quick Links (e.g., *Terms & Conditions*), Project Facts, contact, social media accounts and the newsletter subscription are located. The project facts include the project duration, the reference number and the funding programme.

Figure 15: DECICE Website Structure

3.2 Section “HOME”

Figure 16 shows the front page (“HOME”) of the DECICE website. The *HOME* page displays a header visual of DECICE with the brief topic explanation. This is followed by the newsletter subscription banner, which links to the newsletter registration form. After this call to action, a short overview of the DECICE project as well as an overview of the main objectives is provided. The section Twitter News displays the latest social media posts and gives the opportunity to be informed about most recent news. Finally, the project consortium is presented and highlighted with their individual partner logos.

Figure 16: DECICE Website Section “HOME”

Header

The header of the first page (cf Fig. 17) presents the logo, menu and social media links as well as the header banner.

Following well-grounded best practise [4], the logo in the left upper corner always links back to the first page. To ensure accessibility, basic functions such as accessing menu buttons, the logo (*HOME*) and links on the websites via the tab key have been implemented. This is to help users who want to access different areas of the website without the help of a computer mouse.

Furthermore, the menu highlights the most important information and navigates the visitor clearly and quickly through the website. Additionally, the social media channels are prominently presented in the header and footer, where each website user would search for it because of learned behaviour [5]. This menu bar sticks to the top of the website on every page to always allow the user to navigate through the website.

The image banner embodies the brand identity and attracts with a representative image. The project acronym and brief project description are included for the visitors to be able to come in contact with the essence of the project on their first look.

Figure 17: DECICE Website Section “HOME” – Header

Newsletter Subscription Banner

After the header, the newsletter subscriber banner (cf Fig. 18) is prominently positioned to push the numbers of subscribers, thus having a broad audience to send newsletters to. More information will be provided in this report in section 5 Newsletter.

Figure 18: DECICE Website Section “HOME” – Newsletter Subscription Banner

About DECICE

In the section “About DECICE” (cf Fig. 19) a short description of the project and a representing infographic is provided. The button “More Details” links to the related subpage “ABOUT” for further information.

About DECICE

DECICE aims to develop an **AI-based, open and portable cloud management framework for automatic and adaptive optimization and deployment of applications in a federated infrastructure**, including computing from the very large (e.g., HPC systems) to the very small (e.g., IoT sensors connected on the edge).

Working at such vastly different scales requires an **intelligent management plane with advanced capabilities** that allow it to proactively adjust workloads within the system based on their needs, such as latency, compute power and power consumption. Therefore, we envision an AI-model, which can use a digital twin of the resources available, to make real-time scheduling decisions based on telemetry data from the resources.

The DECICE framework will be able to dynamically balance different workloads, optimize the throughput and latency of the system resources (compute, storage, and network) regarding performance and energy efficiency and quickly adapt to changing conditions.

The framework also gives the necessary **tools and interfaces for the administrators and deployment experts to interface with all the infrastructure components and control them to achieve the desired result**. The integration of the DECICE framework with orchestration systems will be done through open standard APIs to make it portable, modular and extensible

Last but not least any planned clustering activities such as trainings, workshops and webinars will be held in close cooperation with [OEHI](#).

[More Details](#)

Figure 19: DECICE Website Section “HOME” – About DECICE

Project Objectives

The project objectives (cf Fig. 20) are presented with visually appealing DECICE Icons. Additionally, the six objectives are summed up and each keyword is emphasised to help the reader to extract the important information instantly.

DECICE Objectives

- LEVERAGE A COMPUTE CONTINUUM** ranging from Cloud and HPC to Edge and IoT
- AI-SCHEDULER** supporting dynamic load balancing for energy efficient compute orchestration, improved use of Green Energy, and automated deployment.
- API** that increases control over network, computing and data resources.
- DYNAMIC DIGITAL TWIN** of the system with AI-based prediction capabilities
- REAL-LIFE USE CASES** of DECICE framework (usability and benefits).
- SERVICE DEPLOYMENT** with a high level of trustworthiness and compliance with relevant security frameworks.

Figure 20: DECICE Website Section “HOME” – Project Objectives

News

The News section on the *HOME*-page presents the latest DECICE news articles (cf Fig. 21) and invites the reader to get more information about the topic he is interested in. Therefore, a *Call-to-Action (CTA)* button “More Details” was created. This leads to a longer website session duration, a better bounce rate and more returning visitors because of relevant content.

News

FORSCHUNG Burgenland
RESEARCH & INNOVATION

FBU and their contribution to DECICE

DECICE: Cloud-Management mithilfe von Künstlicher Intelligenz
May 12, 2023 /
Die Forschung Burgenland ist einer von 13 Partnern des europaweiten Verbundprojektes DECICE und forscht an neuen Lösungen für die Verwaltung...

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Use Cases Requirements Workshop
20.04.2023

DECICE

Collecting Use Case Requirements for Infrastructure Provisioning in the DECICE EU-Funded Project
May 5, 2023 /
DECICE organised a Use Case Requirements Workshop on the 20th April 2023. The goal of this event was to collect...

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HUAWEI

HUAWEI and their contribution to DECICE

Huawei's Role in the DECICE Project: Leveraging AI for Enhanced Cloud and Edge Computing
April 28, 2023 /
Huawei, a leading global provider of information and communications technology (ICT) infrastructure and smart devices, has recently announced its participation...

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GA GEORG AUGUST-UNIVERSITÄT GÖTTINGEN

UGOE and their contribution to DECICE

The University of Göttingen as coordinator in the DECICE project
April 21, 2023 /
The University of Göttingen (UGOE) is an internationally important research university with a long tradition. The science location Göttingen itself...

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HLRS
High-Performance Computing Center Stuttgart

HLRS and their contribution to DECICE

HPC and the integration of cloud and edge workflows in DECICE
April 14, 2023 /
HLRS (Hochleistungsrechenzentrum Stuttgart/High Performance Computing Center Stuttgart), is excited to participate in the DECICE project. It contributes HPC expertise and...

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UNIBO

UNIBO and their contribution to DECICE

Let's meet the brains behind the DECICE data-driven AI digital twin
March 30, 2023 /
Almost 1000 years old, the University of Bologna (UNIBO) is known as the oldest University in the western world. Nowadays,...

[Read More](#)

[More Details](#)

Figure 21: DECICE Website Section "HOME" – News

Twitter News

The Twitter News section (cf Fig. 22) gives an overview of all recent Twitter posts allowing the users to click on handles, hashtags, retweet, like, share and open DECICE post they are interested in. For more DECICE Twitter posts the visitors can click on the button “View all on Twitter” which links them to the DECICE Twitter account with the whole collection of posts. Furthermore, a call to action “Follow us on LinkedIn” was implemented to highlight the LinkedIn Account as well and gain follower and outreach on social media.

Figure 22: DECICE Website Section “HOME” – Twitter News

Project Consortium

The last content section highlights the consortium partner (cf Fig. 23) with their logos and individual links to their websites. The button “More Details” links the user to the *CONSORTIUM* page for further information and more partner links such as social media accounts, etc.

Figure 23: DECICE Website Section “HOME” – Project Consortium

Footer

The Footer (cf Fig. 24) is like the menu header available on every page of the website. In order to be aligned with the EU Communication and Dissemination Guidelines and with the relevant articles in the GA the Footer provides the DECICE Logo, the EU Logo including funding text and the coordinator's address. Following best practises [6], quick links for instance terms & conditions and contact possibilities such as mail-address, Twitter and LinkedIn links are provided in the footer section at the bottom of the website. Additionally, a main part of the footer represents the project facts like duration, programme information, reference number and CORDIS-link of the project. Finally, a call to action to subscribe to the DECICE newsletter was implemented into the footer to highlight it on every page.

Figure 24: DECICE Website Section "HOME" – Footer

Terms & Conditions

In accordance with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) [7], the website also contains a "Terms & Conditions" subpage (cf Fig. 25), containing information about the handling of personal data, the transfer of data to third parties, data security and a "Disclaimer of liability". In addition, the imprint, restrictions regarding the use of the website, the GDPR and information about the ownership of the website are provided. The "Terms & Conditions" page is linked at the footer section of the webpage, providing contact details of the project coordinator *Georg-August-Universität Göttingen Stiftung Öffentlichen Rechts*. The Imprint, Privacy Policy, Data Security and Newsletter subscription policy can be found under "Terms & Conditions".

Figure 25: DECICE Website Section “HOME” – Footer_Terms & Conditions

3.3 Section “NEWS”

The website *NEWS* section (cf Fig. 26) shows the banner for the newsletter subscription like on the *HOME*-page. Followed by the latest DECICE news articles which are published regularly. This section provides a lot of content related to the project, newest results, partner presentations and much more. As mentioned in the 3.2 Section “*HOME*” - News, relevant content provided on the website is crucial to reach our KPIs and assure a successful project communication and dissemination. Furthermore, Google rates websites with relevant content higher when searching for related topics [8]. Read more in 3.9.1 Search Engine Optimization (SEO). To achieve maximum output, all partners contribute by delivering news articles on a regular basis.

Figure 26: DECICE Website Section "NEWS"

3.3.1 News Article Guide

The following guide (cf Fig. 27) has been created and distributed among the consortium to explain what contributions are expected from the partners in this area. The guide provides an explanation of the spreadsheet used for organisation, tips and tricks and helpful links to examples or to our share point for collection.

Figure 27: DECICE Website Section "NEWS" – Guide

3.4 Section “EVENTS”

The *EVENT* page (cf Fig. 28) provides an overview over content related events such as conferences, workshops, exhibitions, etc. Furthermore, events where DECICE partners are attending and events (co)-organised by DECICE will get presented here as well. This event list is relevant for the consortium, for involved stakeholders, for sister projects and for interested parties to keep track of ongoing events and therefore they will be updated regularly. To easily find events there are filter opportunities such as: *search*, *(co)-organised by DECICE*, *DECICE attending*, *category* and *location* filter along with the possibility to hide previous events. Every event is presented with the title, the organiser, the date and location. Additionally, a category is assigned to every event and a button with the link to the *EVENT* page, for further information and registration, is highlighted. This *EVENT* page helps also to leverage the traffic on the website to achieve the project KPIs.

The screenshot displays the 'EVENTS' section of the DECICE website. It features a light blue header with the word 'EVENTS' in blue. Below the header, there are three main components: a filter sidebar on the left, a title 'Upcoming Events' in purple, and a list of three event cards. Each card includes a calendar icon, the event title, date, organizer, location, and a 'Visit Event Page' button.

Filter event by title
Event title...

(Co-) Organized by DECICE
 DECICE attending

Filter results
Location
Show All ▾
 Hide past events

Upcoming Events

Global IoT Summit 2023
Date: 19.–20.05.2023 | Organised by: Springer; Lecture Notes in Computer Science | Location: Germany (Berlin)
[Visit Event Page](#)

ISC HPC 2023
Date: 21.–25.05.2023 | Organised by: ISC HPC | Location: Germany (Hamburg)
[Visit Event Page](#)

INFN Workshop sul Calcolo
Date: 22.–26.05.2023 | Organised by: Indico | Location: Italy (Savona)
[Visit Event Page](#)

Figure 28: DECICE Website Section “EVENTS”

3.4.1 Events Organized by DECICE

On this subpage, events (co)-organized by DECICE (cf Fig. 29) are highlighted with a representative image and marked in blue colour, which represents the project identity. Additionally, project facts and a link to further information and registration are provided.

The screenshot displays the 'EVENTS' section of the DECICE website. On the left, there are two filter panels. The first panel, 'Filter event by title', contains a search input field labeled 'Event title...'. The second panel contains two toggle switches: '(Co-) Organized by DECICE' (which is turned on) and 'DECICE attending' (which is turned off). Below these is a 'Filter results' panel with a 'Location' dropdown menu set to 'Show All' and a 'Hide past events' toggle switch (turned off). The main content area is titled 'Upcoming Events' and 'Past Events'. It features three event cards, each with a representative image, a title, date, organizer, location, and a 'Visit Event Page' button. The first card is for a 'Use Case Requirements Workshop' on 20.04.2023, organized by TOP-IX, online. The second card is for a 'Kick Off Meeting' on 28.-29.03.2023, organized by GWDG, in Göttingen. The third card is for another 'Kick Off Meeting' on 17.11.2022, organized by GWDG, online.

Figure 29: DECICE Website Section “EVENTS” – (co)-organized by DECICE

3.5 Section “ABOUT”

The “ABOUT” section (cf Fig. 30) provides a general overview of the project, providing the visitor the opportunity to form a well-rounded opinion on the DECICE project. The first section presents the project background, project objectives, project facts and the cooperation with OEHI. These are followed by the project concept, the project impacts and finally the project structure, including the work packages and deliverables. Each section will be explained in the following sections.

Figure 30: DECICE Website Section “ABOUT”

Project Background

This subsection (cf Fig. 31) provides a project overview and presents the main facts. It includes a brief introduction on the background and the relevance of this project.

Figure 31: DECICE Website Section “ABOUT” – Project Background

Project Objectives

The “Project Objectives” subsection (cf Fig. 32) presents an overview of the six objectives of DECICE.

Figure 32: DECICE Website Section “ABOUT” – Project Objectives

Project Facts

In the subsection “Project Facts” (cf Fig. 33) all important basic information about the project is provided. The overview includes the duration of the project, the funding programme and the Grant Agreement reference number. Furthermore, the CORDIS link to the DECICE project is mentioned.

Figure 33: DECICE Website Section “ABOUT” – Project Facts

In cooperation with

Our cooperation with OEHI concerning any planned clustering activities such as trainings, workshops and webinars is highlighted in this subsection (cf Fig. 34) with the link to their website.

Figure 34: DECICE Website Section “ABOUT” – In cooperation with

Project Concept

This subsection describes the project’s concept (cf Fig. 35) including the “AI-based, open and portable cloud management”, the “Digital Twin”, the “DECICE framework” and the “open standard APIs”. The visualisation and brief description support the reader to quickly extract the information needed.

Project Concept

AI-based, open and portable cloud management

DECICE aims to develop an AI-based, open and portable cloud management framework for automatic and adaptive optimization and deployment of applications in a federated infrastructure, including computing from the very large (e.g., HPC systems) to the very small (e.g., IoT sensors connected on the edge).

Digital Twin

Working at such vastly different scales requires an intelligent management plane with advanced capabilities that allow it to proactively adjust workloads within the system based on their needs, such as latency, compute power and power consumption. Therefore, we envision an AI-model, which can use a digital twin of the resources available, to make real-time scheduling decisions based on telemetry data from the resources.

DECICE framework

The DECICE framework will be able to dynamically balance different workloads, optimize the throughput and latency of the system resources (compute, storage, and network) regarding performance and energy efficiency and quickly adapt to changing conditions. The framework also gives the necessary tools and interfaces for the administrators and deployment experts to interface with all the infrastructure components and control them to achieve the desired result.

Open standard APIs

The integration of the DECICE framework with orchestration systems will be done through open standard APIs to make it portable, modular and extensible. The DECICE framework will be evaluated through established use cases.

Figure 35: DECICE Website Section “ABOUT” – Project Concept

Project Impacts

The next subsection “Project Impacts” (cf Fig. 36) presents the three impacts generated by the DECICE project. The moment you hover over one of the impact boxes with the mouse cursor, a short description of the impact will be shown. One the smartphones the text appears after clicking on the box.

Figure 36: DECICE Website Section “ABOUT” – Project Impacts

Project Structure

The “Project Structure” subsection (cf Fig. 37) provides an overview of all work packages (WPs) including a brief description and all deliverables. Compared to public deliverables that will be available for download, sensitive deliverables are not open for public viewing and therefore not downloadable.

Project Structure

+ WP1: Project Management	Click here to view public deliverables
+ WP2: AI Scheduler for Optimization and Adaption	Click here to view public deliverables
+ WP3: Open Framework and Virtual Training Environment	Click here to view public deliverables
+ WP4: Cloud Management Framework Integration	Click here to view public deliverables
+ WP5: Deployment, Validation and Performance Assessment	Click here to view public deliverables
- WP6: Dissemination and Communication	Click here to view public deliverables

WP6 seeks to enhance the impact of the project in the long-term through strategic planning of the dissemination, communication and stakeholder engagement activities.

- D6.1 Dissemination & Communication Plan (Deliverable not available yet)
[Download](#)
- D6.2 Exploitation Strategy (Sensitive deliverable – not open for public viewing)
[Download](#)
- D6.3 Online and Media Presence (Deliverable not available yet)
[Download](#)
- D6.4 Engagement Summary Report (Deliverable not available yet)
[Download](#)

Figure 37: DECICE Website Section “ABOUT” – Project Structure

3.6 Section “CONSORTIUM”

The section “CONSORTIUM” (cf Fig. 38) shows all 13 partners of the consortium. Each partner is presented with their logo, a brief description and with links to their websites and social media accounts. The partners are listed in the same order as mentioned in the Description of the action (DoA), starting with the coordinator UGOE.

Figure 38: DECICE Website Section "CONSORTIUM"

3.7 Section “MEDIA”

The section “MEDIA” (cf Fig. 39) provides the project identity items and print materials ready to download. This page will be updated when new creations are uploaded. At the moment, the following items are possible to download: DECICE Logo Package, DECICE Media Kit, DECICE Project Presentations (short and long), DECICE Posters, DECICE Leaflet, DECICE Roll-Ups (basic or with content), DECICE QR-Code Poster A4, DECICE Sticker Pack (Logo, Icon), DECICE Business Cards, DECICE Folder.

This page is of great use internally and externally. Therefore, the consortium partners have access to relevant print material and project logos, which is important for communication and dissemination of the DECICE project on physical and online events.

Figure 39: DECICE Website Section “MEDIA”

3.8 Section “CONTACT”

The “CONTACT” section (cf Fig. 40) shows the contact details and the location of the project coordinator (*Georg-August-Universität Göttingen Stiftung Öffentlichen Rechts*) embedded in “Google Maps”. For more information about the project or specific enquiries, a mail address (office@decice.eu) and a contact form is provided. This online form requires a name, email address, subject and main body to be filled out. Based on the specific inquiry and the topic, the responsible consortium partner will be notified in order to provide the appropriate response on time. In addition to the DECICE mail address, the social media channels are highlighted as further possibility to get in contact with the project team.

Figure 40: DECICE Website Section “CONTACT”

3.9 Technical Aspects

3.9.1 Search Engine Optimization (SEO)

The website has installed the Yoast SEO plugin, which will increase the visibility of the site. Moreover, it will optimise it for search engines and help the consortium understand readability, keyword density and, most of all, create better content. Finally, it will ensure faster loading times for the DECICE project website, based on innovative ways of managing information in WordPress [9].

Furthermore, the website is connected with Google Webmaster Tools to increase the project index in search engines. In addition to the plugin, SYNNO optimises the content according to SEO and uses crosslinks to get higher Google ratings.

3.9.2 Google Analytics

The project website has the Google Analytics tracking code embedded, which will help us survey the usage of the site from end users in different dimensions like location, language, device, technology, demographic, browser and more. These useful insights will be used for any potentially necessary adjustment of the website in order to continuously attract relevant project stakeholders and general public, as well as to help the consortium to achieve the KPIs accordingly. The use of this plugin is in accordance with GDPR.

3.9.3 Encryption

The website uses the Hypertext Transfer Protocol Secure (HTTPS) as a secure communication protocol, using the Transport Layer Security as encryption.

4 Social Media

In order to attract maximum attention to the DECICE project, accounts on the most relevant social media platforms were created to distribute content. The social media channels will provide communication and updates throughout the duration of the project, in order to reach the desired dissemination and communication impact. The DECICE project utilises a Twitter as well as a LinkedIn account, all created, operated and maintained by SYNIO. Furthermore, a YouTube channel will be set up if required for disseminating the produced videos. Every consortium partner is contributing to the growth of the social media channels by sharing, liking, subscribing, following, engaging or posting regularly. When posting on social media, it is recommended to use the project's handle @DECICE_EU (Twitter), @DECICE Project (LinkedIn) along with @HorizonEU and (Twitter) and @European Commission (LinkedIn). In addition, relevant hashtags like #DECICE #HorizonEU #horizoneurope #europeancommission #HaDEA #CognitiveCloud #edge #Cloud, #IoT #AI #DigitalTwin #CognitiveCloud #Kubernetes #smartcity #HPC etc. will give posts more visibility. Furthermore, the hashtag #DECICE will be used in the project communication. Finally, all partners are tagged in the posts. Due to that, interested parties can find out more information about the consortium partners. Furthermore, the DECICE post and its information is linked to the partners and it is easier for the consortium to share the posts. Therefore, the post achieves more outreach.

4.1 Twitter

As initial communication channel aiming to increase the presence and visibility of DECICE, the Twitter account (@DECICE_EU) has been created, available via https://twitter.com/DECICE_EU (cf Fig. 41). Information about project outcomes, relevant events, publications and similar information, will be shared regularly and whenever appropriate. This platform focuses on a short-form social engagement, content oriented, debate and interaction. Therefore, Twitter is used for growing our audience and expanding the outreach.

Twitter - as open platform - allows access to the information without restricting the end-user (e.g., by requiring registering and logging-in into the platform to access content). Thus, it will be used to disseminate current information about the project scope, as open feedback channels and to establish two-way dialogues with the wider public. Initially, information will be provided about project activities, as well as relevant information related to the DECICE project.

Figure 41: DECICE Social Media – Twitter

4.2 LinkedIn

In comparison to Twitter as short form casual communication, LinkedIn is a more professional network with the focus on connections and can be used for more professional or business-oriented networking leads. To reach a broader audience and have the opportunity to share long-form content as well, the consortium created an DECICE LinkedIn account (@DECICE Project) with the matching handle #DECICE. As shown in figure 42 this account is available via <https://www.linkedin.com/in/decice-project-b0b55b25a/>.

Figure 42: DECICE Social Media – LinkedIn

4.3 Social Media Guide

To support the partners with the creation of the social media posts and familiarise them with the structure created by SYNNO, a guide has been created and sent out. Figure 43 shows this guide with the explanation of the spreadsheet, basic information like the number of characters and tips and tricks for creating social media posts including links and emojis.

Figure 43: DECICE Social Media – Guide

5 Newsletter

SYNYO created a newsletter template using the project identity. People interested in the project can subscribe via DECICE website and by scanning the QR code on a DECICE poster or table stand at events as well as on business card. Furthermore, interested parties can easily subscribe the newsletter through the forwarded [newsletter subscription link](#). To further enlarge our audience for newsletters the subscription opportunity will be added to the registration of our organised events. As shown in figure 44, a signup form has already been implemented. The newsletter will be sent out regularly throughout the project. It will be sent to all relevant stakeholders in the field and will be mainly used as a tool for communicating project updates, disseminating project outcomes or generally for events announcements. The newsletter registration form, which has been embedded on the project website, is designed in accordance with the GDPR requirements respecting the rights of the data subjects, including the appropriate consent text (all users must provide their explicit consent to sign up for the newsletter), as well as the relevant subscription privacy policy. All newsletters will be designed in a GDPR-friendly way and only be sent out to contacts who signed up freely and voluntarily using the form.

Newsletter

Subscribe to our newsletter and get the latest news on the DECICE development and communication activities!

Email

First Name

Last name

I have read the Terms and Conditions on the DECICE project website and I authorize the processing of my personal data under Legislative Decree No. 196/2003 and the 2016/679 European Regulation concerning the protection of personal data of natural persons. [Terms and Conditions](#)

Ich bin kein Roboter.
Datenschutzerklärung - Nutzungsbedingungen

Subscribe

Figure 44: DECICE Newsletter

6 Conclusion

The project website serves as an important resource and as the primary dissemination and communication tool, where our target groups such as industry and innovators, researchers, standardization bodies, initiatives, policymakers and civil society can find significant information about the project. Besides the basic information about the project, especially the upcoming events planned by DECICE and regularly published news articles provided by the partners will help to achieve the KPIs and create significant awareness among potential interested stakeholders. As the project progresses, it is foreseen to expand the project website with further content and subpages if necessary.

In addition to the project website, further dissemination channels and activities such as social media channels were established and will be created in the future according to project needs. A Twitter account as well as a LinkedIn account for DECICE have been set-up and posts are published on a regular basis to ensure a steady increase of followers and raise awareness. Furthermore, during the project lifespan, the website and the social media channels will be continuously enriched with updates and materials from the DECICE project. Additional social media channels such as YouTube, will be implemented depending on the ongoing project results and engagement level with the project audience. The DECICE newsletter will also provide regular updates on project outcomes or events.

All of the project consortium partners will contribute to the growth of the communication channels by either sharing, liking, subscribing, following, engaging or posting regularly. In the “Dissemination and Communication Plan” (D6.1) more details on the communication and dissemination of the DECICE project and their partners can be found.

Project Links

DECICE project website:	https://www.decice.eu/
DECICE newsletter subscription:	https://bit.ly/decice-newsletter
DECICE Twitter account:	https://twitter.com/DECICE_EU
DECICE LinkedIn account:	https://www.linkedin.com/in/decice-project-b0b55b25a/

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